

SOCIAL SCIENCES

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND TRANSFORMATION TO THE METASOCIUM

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the expanding processes of digitalization of public life and an active development of artificial intelligence (AI), which together create some new social reality - a metasocium. In fact, this is a second reality, or artificial reality, which scientists sometimes call virtual, sometimes call second reality. Currently, we are witnessing how active human activity is gradually being transferred to this man-made environment. In this regard, the problems of the increasingly complex dynamics of social development are discussed, in the context of modern trends in the nonlinearity of the new world order. Particular attention is paid to analyzing the impact of new forms of artificial intelligence (AI) that have become widespread, as well as the benefits and risks associated with the rapid entry of artificial intelligence into our social life. In particular, new social trends that have emerged after the COVID Pandemic are considered, such as remote work, digital technologies and the transfer of many forms of human activity to the virtual reality.

Keywords: metasocium, social digitalization, artificial intelligence, remote work, digital nomad.

Introduction

Modern social and digital challenges, combined with the crisis of the unipolar world model, as well as the processes of digitalization of reality, are putting forward the need to develop a new concept of causality in sociological theory. American sociologist Edward Tiryakian emphasized that modern challenges existing within civilization have a non-linear impact on the all human life practices [Tiryakian, 2014, 91-112]. This requires the development of fundamentally new types of modernization. In the conditions of the transition from modernity to postmodernity, human society was existed in the form of a more or less stable community.

The nature of this relatively common life activity the sociologists have studied within the framework of certain "objective" patterns of social development. However, subsequent processes of modernization led to the gradual transformation of technology into the relatively independent intellectual and technical substance. The expansion of digitalization processes and the active intervention of artificial intelligence (AI) have brought closer the possibility of step-by-step "humanization" of robots. Sociologists are concerned about such complicated dynamics of the social development. Jean Baudrillard once remarked that there is no longer a "pure" society, and that, in essence, this leads to the "end of the social" [Baudrillard, 1983]. Sociologists began to turn to interdisciplinary concepts that take into account modern trends in the nonlinearity and complexity of the new world order in the context of a growing digital format.

In sociology, attempts are being made to comprehend some new nonlinear directions in the social developments. The English sociologist J. Urry suggested that the hybridization of social and material worlds leads to their "complete intertwining", which contributes to the "alternativeness of future societies" and to the multiplicity of variations. [Urry, 2011, 8].

The well-known "Giddens paradox" speaks about the effect of complicating risks in the coordinates of space and time [Giddens, 2009, 2-3]. The essence of this paradox is that the accelerating dynamics of nature and society, not supported by adequate moral norms of human activity, can generate man-made risks with unforeseen negative consequences delayed in time.

Sociologists began to interpret modernization as a "secondary axial revolution", coupled with the need to solve new ontological contradictions [Eisenstad, 1995]. In this context, interdisciplinary sociological theories are in demand, based on taking into account modern trends in the complexity and nonlinearity of the new world order, the hybridization of socio-digital and natural reality. The time has come when many ideas previously related to the field of science fiction are becoming quite achievable. This opens up great prospects for humanity, but, on the other hand, causes legitimate concerns, since the possibility of mistakes and various abuses along the way is very high [Polozhikhina, 2022, 8].

According to a number of experts, humanity has reached the maximum indicators for the species *Homo sapiens*. People have been engaged in artificial improvement of the human body for a long time. Today,

even a person's cognitive abilities can be improved through the use of special tools. Artificial modification of the human body in the future can replace its spontaneous evolution. Serious developments are currently underway intensively and impressive results have already been achieved in the field of artificial intelligence (AI) and digital transformation of society.

Social problems of AI

So far, AI creates texts from what is on the Internet, i.e. from everything that is available in the digital information database, in the cloud environment and in search programs such as Google, Wikipedia, Yandex and others. In other words, AI does not create anything fundamentally new yet, but glues together, forms from what has already been published, created by others. AI cannot create new knowledge yet, but only combines what is already available. Note that even in this case, the possibilities for diversity are almost limitless. In 5-10 years, AI will create such an extensive virtual reality that it will be difficult to distinguish it from the real one.

The all-powerful Hollywood has been stubbornly and consistently creating this second, invented reality for decades. At the same time, the fictional reality sometimes strongly influenced the real reality. For many years in a row, this interpenetration of two realities took place; a kind of interference of virtual and real reality. Similarly, AI plots are both real and far-fetched, artificial so much that it is difficult to distinguish. J. Baudrillard, describing the postmodern model of society, used the term "hyperreality". He describes a state in which a person cannot distinguish reality from simulation, since all objects of the physical world are replaced by images and signs, which he called "simulacra". [Baudrillard, 1981]. So, a huge part of the microcosm and the macrocosm are simply inaccessible to us due to the limitations of our cognitive abilities. We create an idea about them based on indirect, sometimes purely mathematical calculations and models. What is it, if not a kind of virtual, or "fake reality"? It turns out that in science we have been dealing with virtual reality for a long time. And now we face it in our everyday life.

Concerns about the development of AI

All those fears that have arisen with such a rapid invasion of AI into our lives seem somewhat exaggerated, given that it will not be able to completely replace man in all his manifestations. The fact is that, despite its superhuman abilities, AI lacks the human intuition that so often helps us in our lives. In addition, AI is devoid of human emotions. He is not happy, does not worry, does not get angry or sad, cannot be bored or worried, does not feel creative inspiration and does not fall into sad thoughts. In short, AI is devoid of all those emotions that often motivate a creative person to make the new masterpieces and new ideas. AI never gets tired, does not sleep and does not have dreams that can sometimes overshadow a scientist and an artist. AI cannot love another; he does not know the feeling of love that has inspired many poets, artists and composers to

create immortal works, and scientists to make great discoveries. AI is incapable of envy, hatred, or joking; it has no sense of humor, like all other human feelings. He is completely devoid of emotions, and therefore devoid of the ability to fantasize, dream, create new things. In other words, AI is still a supernova, advanced, modified, but only some "super computer". As the researchers note, the philosophical analysis of AI confirms the significant differences between humans and computers. [Rezaev, 2023, 18].

AI can do a lot of things that a human can never do. But he can't do what a human can. In addition, important developments in the field of human superintelligence can be expected in the near future. This may happen in the next ten years, when gene modification technologies such as the recently discovered CRISPR/Cas system, which caused a revolution in genetic engineering, will appear. To do this, you will need to directly correct the human genome. This opinion was recently expressed in article "The age of superintelligent people is coming"⁹ by Stephen Hsu, Vice-President for Research and Professor of Theoretical Physics at Michigan State University and a scientific advisor to BGI (Beijing Genomics Institute), and a founder of its Cognitive Genomics Lab. [Hsu S., 2014]. Therefore, AI is unlikely to be able to replace humans in all areas of their activities. But in many areas, he is simply irreplaceable. As, for example, in future space flights over long distances. Because AI does not sleep, does not eat, does not get sick, does not feel fear or loneliness, never forgets anything, is always collected, concentrated, calm and reasonable. AI is indispensable in extreme conditions and for making quick decisions. There is no doubt that it will find the widest application in almost all areas of industry, science, technology, economics, transport and security.

Neural network capabilities

During the preparing this article, we formulated a task for a neural network through the OpenAI Chat GPT4 portal. The task consisted of a request to write an article on the topic "What is artificial intelligence". We wanted to see how the AI neural network describes itself and how it wants to present itself in our eyes. In just a couple of seconds, the Chat GPT4 neural network sent a completely coherent and logical text. There was nothing new or unexpected about it. In fact, it was not the original text that the artificial intelligence generated about itself, but a meaningful set of expressions, definitions and descriptions made by a person about AI, and posted on the Internet. For comparison, we formulated a similar task for the Google search engine and received a huge set of different texts, including descriptions of artificial intelligence, its advantages, capabilities, examples of its use, as well as the dangers that it can pose. In addition, a detailed history of the emergence of AI was given, starting with the term "artificial intelligence", which was introduced in 1956 by John McCar-

⁹ https://www.golosarmenii.am/article/182350/gryadet-epoxa-sverxrazumnyx-lyudej?fbclid=IwAR2u6Nb9Lzm-Aj-LhJbc5kDB4T2PodU4pxCdqiKU4XGfDyQJo_Up-GPFGiZXU (accessed data: 15.06.2023).

thy at the first-ever AI conference at Dartmouth College¹⁰. The chronology of its development was presented, from 1842, when the first programmable mechanical calculation machine was created - until 2016, when Google's AlphaGo artificial intelligence defeated the world champion in the game Go. Then one of the best Telegram bots ChatGPT was given, as the embodiment of artificial intelligence from Elon Musk¹¹, which is able to answer all questions, as well as generate ideas, write texts independently and much more.

Attempts to limit the expansion of AI

As known, the ChatGPT's headquarters is located in San Francisco, where people are working hard on its further improvement. Now AI is being trained to imitate people, make films, give interviews on behalf of another person and in his voice. In the summer of 2023, Hollywood actors held a big strike and protests against the use of AI in the production of new films, in which the directors assigned secondary roles not to actors, but replaced them with avatars of these actors generated using AI. As a result, the real actors were left without work. New models of ChatGPT 5th and 6th versions will have the opportunity to influence people, penetrate social networks and manipulate public opinion. AI will be able to create hundreds of thousands of humanoid bots that will have an impact on the mass consciousness. One of the creators of AI, Elon Musk, in his recent interview: "Our future is under threat" responsibly stated that AI could become a threat to society and civilization¹². He is already learning how to lie and tomorrow he will present himself as a living person in order to use us for his own purposes. Musk predicted that everything is heading towards the fact that artificial intelligence will begin to make decisions for people, and has the "potential to destroy civilization." He called on humanity to start regulating this sphere as soon as possible and create a special and responsible agency¹³. In this regard, a number of scientists have called for the suspension of development in the field of AI, until laws regulating and restricting its activities and international treaties are adopted.

From the point of view of sociology, AI is interesting because it makes obvious the problems of the development of artificial sociality. Technologies such as ChatGPT open up new, previously unpredictable possibilities for transforming human dependence on algorithms. [Rezaev, 2023, 16]. As Susan Lindbergh notes in her new book, "Many new historians of our time are studying how algorithmic management shapes the psyche and society today." [Lindberg, 2023, 140].

Transition to Metasocium

Today, upgraded and improved G-Bard V2 models have already appeared, which are 50 times smarter than the old version. They perform natural language

processing, search engine optimization, image and video processing, added reality and virtual reality, offer personalized content and solve the most difficult tasks. Due to the high demand for them, the creators have launched a free trial version of G-Bard V2 for everyone. But researchers have gone further and are now talking about creating the next generation of Internet platforms, which has been dubbed the "metauniverse." [Ball, 2020]. These are a kind of self-sufficient worlds, whose users will be able to work, relax, study and do their various things in them. The founder of "Meta" Mark Zuckerberg described the metauniverse world as "the internet where you're on, not just looking at it."¹⁴ The goal of the metauniverse is to create new ways of interacting between people and to digitalize real life. There is no single matrix in the world of the metauniverse, it is a reality in which the space is created by the users themselves. By February 2022, more than 10,000 virtual worlds had already been built. The number of monthly active users has already exceeded several hundred thousand people. The metauniverse includes a three-dimensional digital space that uses virtual reality or augmented reality technologies, as well as artificial intelligence and blockchain.

In his book, Matthew Bull wrote that by 2026, one in four of us will spend at least an hour a day in the metauniverse: working, studying, communicating and making the necessary purchases [Ball, 2020]. However, recent sociological studies have shown that even today students have increased the amount of time spent on the Internet several times. So, if in 2008 40% of students spent 1-2 hours a day online, then in 2023 83% of students spend more than 4 hours a day. There were cases when students spent "all their free time" on the networks, and for some this figure reached up to 10 hours [Lesnoy, 2023, 62]. In fact, this is a new virtual reality, an artificially created Internet sphere, in which real life is gradually being transferred to a digital platform. Thus, the metasocium is gradually beginning to displace real sociality, digitizing many forms of human activity.

The very prefix "meta" means that the metasocium will allow people to plunge into a virtual world that is not burdened by the limitations of the physical world. This freedom contains both the fundamental advantages and disadvantages of the new reality. The metaspace allows people to work fully without leaving home. Everyone remembers well how, due to the COVID-19 pandemic in 2019-2020, many switched their work to the remote format. This, of course, led to an even greater fragmentation of society, to a sharp reduction in real social contacts between people. However, the COVID is gone, but the remote work remains. And

¹⁰ <https://home.dartmouth.edu/about/artificial-intelligence-ai-coined-dartmouth> (accessed data: 03.04.2024).

¹¹ Elon Musk Building Rival of AI Chatbot ChatGPT. <https://www.ndtv.com/feature/elon-musk-building-rival-of-ai-chatbot-chatgpt-calls-it-3831103> (accessed data: 03.04.2024).

¹² <https://vc.ru/future/753244-nashe-budushchee-pod-ugrozoy-volnuyushchee-intervyu-ilona-maski-ob-ugroze-ii> (accessed data: 11.07.2023).

¹³ <https://dobro.press/novosti/ilon-mask-predryok-gibel-chelovechestva-ot-iskusstvennogo-intellekta> (accessed data: 11.07.2023).

¹⁴ Into the metaverse: What is it? <https://engati.medium.com/into-the-metaverse-what-is-it-960a22c6cea3> (accessed data: 02.04.2024)

this will probably be even more in the future. A new generation, so called “digital generation” of young people has appeared, for whom “remote” working has become a new way of life, the style of new generation. Since 1997, physician David Manners and physicist Tsugio Makimoto published the book "Digital Nomad" [Makimoto, 1997]. According this book, active digital travelers have replaced those who work on the remote and those who work at home.

Conclusion

The essence of the lifestyle of the digital generation is permanent movement, expansion of their capabilities. Today a people, thanks to mobile communication and IT, is not tied to a specific place of work or study. The first wave of "digital nomad" consists of programmers and IT specialists. Their favorite places of movement are island Bali in Indonesia, islands in Thailand and Goa state in India. The most common professions among them are “e-commerce”, designers, marketers, copywriters, translators, data analysts, web developers, testing engineers, “big data analysts” and even accountants. Changing their place of residence and changing their profession becomes for them a conscious step towards development, “improving the version of themselves.” They live in a world full of uncertainty, in which circumstances often change and in which the borders of States are erased. They have made movement a model of their behavior, a new cult, a global trend [Beverly, 2019, 1-17]. Especially for this purpose, places of joint residence and work, the so-called “coworking” and “colivings”, have appeared in various countries. Something like cafes and hotels, but with a different content. Coworking spaces have replaced usual offices and noisy cafes with poor internet access. And “colivings” have become dormitories of interest for digital nomads from all over the world. We unexpectedly encountered this new social trend in Armenia when the Ukrainian war and Western sanctions against Russia forced many Russians to leave the country [Poghosyan, 2023, 52-61].

In the summer of 2022, about 150,000 Russians arrived in Armenia. Of these, 70 thousand opened accounts in Armenian banks, moved their business, sometimes together with office workers. Most of them are young people, representatives of small and medium-sized businesses, IT companies and internet specialists, whom we have dubbed “relocators” [Integration VS Repatriation, 2022, 193]. By now, more than 20 thousand relocators have managed to obtain a second citizenship in Armenia. For our country, this is a great acquisition both economic, financial, demographic, professional and cultural. Taking into account the new behaviors of digital nomad, it is probably worth designing the economic space for the near future in such a way that the coming generation of young people can comfortably use it for moving and relocating their business.

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